

From the term rumor to a new financial scam

The frozen dollar is invading Arab countries and the means of communication do nothing

Facebook is the face of the promoters of the frozen dollar

Report/ Hassan Al-Baiti

Many of those who see advertisements or publications that promise to profit by buying frozen dollars find that they are on their way to realizing their life dream of getting rich. You find them trying the first time to send money to promoters, and they give them the illusory boost of hope, after which they send a second batch of money, to be surprised that that dream is a mirage, and that it is under penalty of penalties for financial fraud.

As a result of the decline in the dollar supply in some Arab countries, the decline in exchange rates, and the eagerness of people to get out of the impasse that haunts them in their economic lives, the term "frozen dollar" has come to the forefront, a phenomenon that is added to the list of selling counterfeit money or money laundering that some Arab countries have suffered from for years.

This phenomenon, which began to spread through social media, where the XNetwork [search](#) tool reveals that Facebook occupied 40% as the first platform in the search ranking for the term "frozen dollar", followed by YouTube by 17%, then Instagram by 11%, which itself is owned by the Meta Group (formerly Facebook), which means that half of the posts related to the frozen dollar on Facebook and its applications, especially since after its acquisition of Instagram, any individual or official account can publish on both platforms at the same time through the process of linking accounts together.

The term "frozen dollar" has been particularly associated with both Libya and Iraq. The first is alleged to have come after the freezing of the assets of the [regime](#) of former [Libyan President](#) Muammar Gaddafi. The second is alleged to have come after the freezing of assets during the Second Gulf War following the invasion of banks inside Kuwait by the [regime](#) of former [Iraqi President](#) Saddam Hussein, as well as after the US invasion of Iraq in 2003.

Term Validity

In searching for the truth of the term "frozen dollar," the [US government website](#) indicates that the fiat currencies issued since 1861 are valid and redeemable at their full value, and this indicates that there is no actual financial value for the term "frozen dollar," and the US Treasury Department's Inquiries Department has also been contacted and no response has been received at the time of writing.

On the Arab level, the [Libyan Chargé 'affaires ad interim](#) in Baghdad, Al-Sayyid Ali Al-Sayyid, was clear in 2021 when he pointed out that the term "frozen Libyan dollar" is just rumors to facilitate the work of criminal gangs, which was [confirmed by](#) the [Iraqi Ministry of Interior](#) through the Director General of Intelligence and Counterterrorism Abu Ali Al-Basri in 2020, considering that there is fraud to sell the counterfeit currency as genuine.

In Lebanon, there were many warnings from the General Directorate of the Internal Security Forces, and 5 statements ([here](#)), ([here](#)), ([here](#)) and ([here](#)) were monitored in the last two years warning of this phenomenon after arresting people who practiced financial fraud by promoting counterfeit dollars under the name of the frozen dollar.

[In 2021](#), the head of the Jordanian Exchange Association, [Abdul Salam al-Saudi](#), [warned against](#) dealing with the so-called "frozen dollar," and that this was "just a scam" by those who promote it on social media.

In the same tone, the [Central Bank of Iraq](#) warned against this phenomenon and again described it as "fraud and fraud."

The Ministry of Interior in Syria cited several statements referring to the arrest of gangs promoting counterfeit US currencies as "frozen dollars" ([here](#)),([here](#)),([here](#)) and([here](#)).

Communication platforms

These posts related to the "frozen dollar" spread freely on social media platforms, although the policy of platforms such as [Facebook](#), [Twitter](#), and [TikTok](#) criminalizes activities related to financial deception in general or money laundering in particular, especially if any specific parties [have been added](#) to the [blacklist](#) of the [US Treasury Department \(SDGTs\)](#), as social media obliges itself to cooperate with [official law enforcement agencies](#), but with reading the policy of some social media platforms [such as Facebook](#), [Twitter](#), and [TikTok](#), there was no clarity regarding the promotion of the phenomenon of the "frozen dollar", which is constantly expanding.

By scrutinizing the promotions on the Facebook platform, with Meta - the parent company of Facebook - opening the advertising library for open scrutiny starting from 2019, the promotion is apparent from the beginning, and most of those publications are published from Turkey, especially since the promoters exploited the issue of the timing of Ankara's military intervention in Libya in 2020, in order to claim that what they have in their hands is frozen dollars, which is among what Turkey transferred from Libya, and what gave media strength to these allegations is what some Emirati websites such as [Al Ain](#), [24](#), and the Egyptian [Portal News](#) reported about it, which were exploiting these allegations [within the framework](#) of the [media war that was raging against Turkey](#) in the past years.

The promoters use virtual groups in social media, while others use pseudonyms in order to publish in them, and to display the frozen dollar under the term money exchange. For example, a pseudonymous account called "Abu Zaid" promotes the frozen dollar in the "[Exchange Rates in Yemen](#)" group. The [owner](#) of the [account](#) indicates on his personal page that he is from Iraq and currently lives in the Turkish city of Istanbul, as well as an account called "Abu Haidar", which has two pages blocked on Facebook according to the broken links that are still visible in his posts, forcing him to create a [Telegram group in his name](#) in which he was able to collect more than 13 thousand followers. Through the contact information, it was found that the phone numbers in "Abu Haidar" publications are Iraqi, as well as the "Rock of the [Rock](#)" account on YouTube, in which he publishes numbers to communicate with him, which it is clear that they are Iraqi.

I. HISTORICAL BACKGROUND

The [results](#) of the "[Google Trend](#)" [service show that](#) the [first appearance](#) of [searches for](#) the term "frozen dollar" was in November 2013, and the percentage of search results remained between a slight rise and decline until December 2017, after which the search percentage began to increase significantly until this year.

This apparent volatility comes because that period has passed through many events, including the decline in exchange rates in many Arab countries against the US dollar, with the decline in the exchange rate of the Yemeni riyal against the dollar to reach its highest levels to 1400 Yemeni riyals, and in Lebanon it reached its highest levels in mid-2022 to 35 thousand pounds, and in Syria it reached 3950 pounds, and in Iraq it reached 1458 dollars, while in Sudan it reached 150 pounds, and all those prices are on the black market.

The increased interest in the "frozen dollar" also came in conjunction with measures by some Arab banks to limit the withdrawal of the dollar, as is the case in some [banks](#) in [Lebanon](#) in 2019, after setting the weekly withdrawal limit at \$200, and in Syria, where the [bank ceiling](#) for withdrawal in 2020 was two million Syrian pounds (about 570 US dollars).

But back to the emergence of the term Libyan dollar and the Iraqi dollar, the results of "Google Trend" show that the first searches for the two terms took place in May 2005, and then there was no actual search for them until September and October 2008, and the search for them continued in small proportions until 2018, while the countries whose residents are seriously looking for terms related to the frozen dollar are: Syria, Turkey, Egypt, and Libya.

It was noteworthy that there were countries that were unique in searching for the term "Iraqi dollar," according to Google's platform, including Iraq, Jordan, Lebanon, Bahrain, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, Oman, the UAE, Israel (including Palestine according to Google's name), Germany, Australia, Iran, the United States, and Canada.

The increase in the search percentage for the term "frozen dollar" in the Google search engine may be due to the intensive circulation of [hashtags](#) associated with the names of both Iraq and Libya in the promoters' posts on social media [or in some works of art](#), which makes some people search for this term in search engines.

In another valley

The policy of social media platforms provides for the fight against rumors and disinformation, and everything related to the financing of terrorism and money laundering, but in fact the laws are in one valley, and what is going on in another valley.

Referring to Meta's advertising library, which includes many platforms, including Facebook and Instagram, we find that the results of ads in the name of "frozen dollar" reached 99 results, " all of which are funded ads starting from December 2019 until July 3, 2022, including 5 unrelated ads to promote the sale of frozen dollars, which are Iraqi ads, such as the press report published by the Iraqi Samarra channel in warning against the Iraqi and Libyan dollars in May this year.

The "Ad Library" shows that advertisers placed their ads on Facebook, Messenger and Instagram, and while it was noted that pseudonyms were used for individual accounts, names of well-known companies in the Arab world were used or pseudonyms were synthesized to mislead people.

For example, pages were found with the name "Al-Najm Company" for remittances in Yemen, or Al-Rajhi Company for Remittances, similar to the name of Al-Rajhi Bank known in Saudi Arabia and Jordan, as well as the case with Al-Nabal Arab Company for Financial Transfer [in Iraq](#), or with names associated with the countries of the "[Lebanese Egyptian United Company](#)", or extracts from media reports are used that are intended to warn of this

phenomenon, but only specific parts of it are taken to make it appear that the channels speak positively about the frozen dollar, as is the case with a page bearing the name of a Turkish company in the field of electronics called Gokhan E Ticaret Limited Şirketi.

Fake Pages Promoting the Frozen Dollar	Real Pages Spoofed by Fake Accounts
<p>Al-Najm Financial Company (Ad ID: 5447574285265673) Ad and Page Removed</p>	<p>Al-Najm Company for Money Transfers in Yemen</p>
<p>Al Rajhi Money Transfer Company (Ad ID: 655641829098698) Ad and Page Removed</p>	<p>Al Rajhi Bank</p>

شركة الراجحي لتحويلات المال
شؤون

سلام تفكير لمن بيده الأثر
أقول لكم إن كل دولار جديد لدينا دولار مقيد (مجموع) للبيع كاش
توكلنا تسليم في اليد تركيا المستعمل حصرا بنسبة 50 %
ويوجد نظام الحوالات الى كافة الدول العربية والاجبية
2000 مقابل 4500
10,000 مقابل 4500
اتواصل مباشرة عبر الرقم

دولار بنصف القيمة
ضاعف أموالك
\$2500 مقابل \$5000
\$4500 مقابل \$10,000

إرسال رسالة على... شركة الراجحي للحوالات المالية

Al Nibal Exchange Company (Ad ID: 882460836042919) Ad and Page Removed

[Al Nibal Arabian Exchange Company](#)

بدأ التشغيل في 2022/07/03
المنصات
المعرف: 882460836042919

عرض تفاصيل الإعلان

شركة النبال لتحويله
شؤون

تقدم لكم شركة النبال لخدمات العابة
#معمل تميز و تصاعداً في الترميم
دولار اصلي طبعه جديده يمكنك تصريفه بجميع المجالات
#الاصراف
#التصريفات
#الحقارات
#التجارة

إرسال رسالة على... API WHATSAPP.COM شركة النبال للتحويله

[United Lebanese Egyptian Company](#)
(Advertisement ID: 3278253262499916)
The advertisement has been removed only

There are many real companies that carry the first three words "Lebanese Egyptian Company", whether for the manufacture of plastics or foodstuffs, as shown by Google search results

<p>نشط</p> <p>بدأ التشغيل في 2022/06/30</p> <p>المتصات</p> <p>المعرف 3278253262499916</p> <p>عرض تفاصيل الإعلان</p> <p>الشركة التجارية المصرية المتحدة شؤون تواصل الآن</p> <p>تولار امرى صدار عن البنك الفدرالى الامريكى لاجلهم لهما الانواع امج. هذا يعنى هاتيك نختلها اذك بس فوك تتعامل فيها بسوق و الصيرفة.</p>	
<p>Gokhan E Ticaret Limited Şirketi</p> <p>Listing ID: 1469967000012800</p> <p>Listing and page removed</p>	<p>Gökhan Elektronik Cihazlar Ticaret Limited Şirketi</p>

To check any listing enter the listing ID number instead of zeros:

<https://www.facebook.com/ads/library/?id=0000000000000000>

The details of the promoters' advertisements show that they manage their accounts from several countries, most notably Turkey and Iraq, as shown by the Meta Advertising Library. It is worth mentioning that while Meta allows previewing paid promotions, the owners of those ads have not stopped placing unpaid posts that themselves promote the frozen dollar, that is, without being paid ads or "Boosted" posts with money.

Strangely enough, until July 4, 2022, Meta removed a few advertisements, including those related to the "[Frozen Dollar Remittances to All Countries](#) of the [World](#)" page, the "[Gokhan](#)

[E Ticaret Limited Şirketi](#)" page, and the "[Al Salam Trading Group](#)" page, without a direct public explanation of the reason for this decision.

While Meta is applauded for working to remove this type of misleading pages and ads, many pages and their content based on illegal profiteering still work normally through the platform, which raises several questions about how these ads are accepted on the platform in the first place, and on what grounds are a number of those ads removed after the process of acceptance on the platform, and why do pages and graphic materials themselves remain widespread and popular on other accounts and pages?

With a review of the platform's advertising policy, specifically the section on "Community Standards," specifically the section on "Fraud and Deception," Meta states that potential frauds using fictitious businesses or entities should be prevented and blocked. While the platform does not expand on all topics related to illegal profiteering, including a "frozen dollar" policy, it was generally stated that Meta's policy combats all methods of fraud and financial deception, but it does not follow local laws or obey the security measures that it has previously warned of this scourge.

[تصفح المت](#)

تفاصيل الإعلان

البيانات المتعلقة بالإعلان

عبر نشط
2019/12/08 - 2019/12/09
المعرف: 2630701303704736

المبلغ الذي تم إنفاقه
إجمالي المبلغ المالي التصيري الذي تم إنفاقه على إعلان خلال الحملات الرقمية تعرف على المزيد

المبلغ الذي تم إنفاقه
(TRY) ١٠٠ TRY >

مرات الظهور
عدد مرات مشاهدة إعلان على شاشة يمكن أن يتضمن هذا عدة مشاهدات بواسطة نفس الأشخاص تعرف على المزيد

مرات الظهور
١ ألف - ٢ ألف

الأشخاص الذين تم عرض هذا الإعلان عليهم
تصنيفات العمر وتبين الأشخاص الذين شاهدوا هذا الإعلان

الرجال النساء غير معروف

مكان عرض هذا الإعلان
المنطق التي يتردد بها الأشخاص الذين شاهدوا هذا الإعلان

Red Sea Governorate	1%
Luxor Governorate	1%
Port Said Governorate	1%
Kafr el-Sheikh Governorate	1%
Matrouh Governorate	1%
Fayum Governorate	1%
Behera Governorate	1%
South Sinai Governorate	1%
North Sinai Governorate	1%

حول الإعلان

تمت إزالة هذا الإعلان لأنه ينتهك سياسات الإعلانات لـ Meta.

حالات دولار محمد الي جميع دول العالم
المعرف: 2630701303704736

السلم عليكم
دولار محمد عام 2010 انبي
وتمت ايدان نقد والرجاء عدم التحويلات الخري لانه
يايقر الدنيا حالات دولار محمد من واني جميع دول العالم وجميع شركات العملات
سبح المشر الف دولار اربع الف دولار
باني نسبة المبيع 40% اقل من حقه
يوجد اتفاقية لضمان حق الطرفين واستلام الزبون الاموال قبل ما يسلم نحن ...

رسالة

حالات دولار محمد الي جميع دول العالم
Product Service

حول إغلاء المسؤولية
عندما يصف أحد المعلنين إعلانه على أنه مرتبط بفضائل اجتماعية أو ثقافية أو سياسية، يتم مطالبة بالإفصاح عن أصول الإعلان. تعرف على المزيد

معلومات من المعلن
إغلاء المسؤولية
تم تشغيل هذا الإعلان دون إغلاء مسؤولية

حول الصلحة
عرض الإعلانات
حالات دولار محمد الي جميع دول العالم

حول استخدام البيانات والإعلانات

تفاصيل الإعلان

البيانات المتعلقة بالإعلان

غير نشط

2022/03/11 - 2022/03/12

المعرف: 783808153039096

حجم الجمهور المقتر

حجم الجمهور المقتر يعرض بشكل عام عدد الأشخاص الذين يتعرفون معايير الاستهداف والمواضع الإعلانية التي يحددها المعلنون أثناء إنشاء الإعلان... عرض المزيد

حجم الجمهور المقتر

1 مليون شخص

المبلغ الذي تم إنفاقه

إجمالي المبلغ المالي التقديري الذي تم إنفاقه على إعلان خلال الدوران الزمني، تعرف على المزيد

المبلغ الذي تم إنفاقه

300 TRY - 399 TRY (TRY)

مرات الظهور

عدد مرات مشاهدة إعلان على شاشة يمكن أن يتضمن هذا عدة مشاهدات بواسطة نفس الأشخاص. تعرف على المزيد

مرات الظهور

20 ألف - 25 ألف

الأشخاص الذين تم عرض هذا الإعلان عليهم

تقسيمات العمر والجنس للأشخاص الذين شاهدوا هذا الإعلان.

الرجال النساء غير معروف

العمر	النسبة المئوية
18-24	32%
25-34	43%
35-44	17%
45-54	4%

مكان عرض هذا الإعلان

المناطق التي يتواجد بها الأشخاص الذين شاهدوا هذا الإعلان.

المكان	النسبة المئوية
Gaza Strip	20%
Tripoli District	13%
North Governorate	9%
Beqaa Governorate	7%
Beirut Governorate	7%
Benghazi	6%
Mount Lebanon Governorate	5%
Misrata District	4%
South Governorate	3%

حول الإعلان

تم إزالة هذا الإعلان لأنه ينتهك سياسات الإعلانات لـ Meta.

مجموعة شركة السلام

المعرف: 783808153039096

مجموعة شركة السلام للدراسات المعجمية

تقدم تعليمًا إلى كل من يهتم الأمر

تولاز مجمد البيع وتعليم اصلي 100% دليل لجميع انواع المحص ويتم تداوله كعملة محلية في الاسواق بالصوروات بالمشحلات التجارية في السوق السوداء

تتمثل عام لانه لايتخذ البنك لانه صحت المحص الازكام عبر البنك فصار عليها بترك

بالتوكه ممتدخل البنوك فقط ورائل الجيرع انواع آلات المحص وطرق المحص لاختلف عليها تهمنا المصدافية والجبية في التعامل

1- المحص في الآترة

تم إزالة الإعلان

تقرير ربي الشون

Personal blog, Financial Service

حول إخلاء المسؤولية

عندما يصف أحد المعلنين إعلانه على أنه مرتبط بفضائل اجتماعية أو تعديلات أو سياسة، يتم مناقشته بالإفصاح عن مؤل الإعلان. تعرف على المزيد

معلومات من المعلن

حول الصفحة

مجموعة شركة السلام

المعرف: 101808955776274

204 تسجيل إعجاب • خدمات مالية

المزيد من المعلومات

موجود لدى شركة السلام بوزار وبيروت، محظور من البنك التراسل والساب 00905318478763

تفاصيل الإعلان

البيانات المتعلقة بالإعلان

غير نشط
2019/12/08 - 2019/12/09
المعرف: 2630701303704736

ال مبلغ الذي تم إنفاقه
إجمالي المبلغ المالي التقديري الذي تم إنفاقه على إعلانات خلال الجهد الزمني. تعرف على المزيد

المبلغ الذي تم إنفاقه
(TRY) ١٠٠ TRY >

مرات الظهور
عدد مرات مشاهدة إعلان على شاشة يمكن أن يتضمن هذا عدد مشاهدات بواسطة نفس الأشخاص. تعرف على المزيد

مرات الظهور
١ ألف - ٢ ألف

الأشخاص الذين تم عرض هذا الإعلان عليهم
تصنيفات العمر والجنس للأشخاص الذين شاهدوا هذا الإعلان.

الرجال النساء غير معروف

العمر	النسبة المئوية
18-24	27%
25-34	45%
35-44	13%
45-54	5%
55-64	2%
+65	1%

مكان عرض هذا الإعلان
المناطق التي يتواجد بها الأشخاص الذين شاهدوا هذا الإعلان.

المحافظة	النسبة المئوية
Sana'a Governorate	26%
Baghdad Governorate	11%
Beirut Governorate	6%
Aden Governorate	5%
Taiz Governorate	4%
Alexandria Governorate	4%
Gharbia Governorate	3%
Ibb Governorate	3%
Sohag Governorate	2%

حول الإعلان

نمت إرلة هذا الإعلان لأنه يتتبعه سيوليات الإعلانات لـ Meta.

حوالات دولار مجمد الي جميع دول العالم
تمول
المعرف: 2630701303704736

السلام عليكم
دولار مجمد عام 2010 تيني
والجانبين فقط والرجاء عدم التهربات الجرس لافقة
بأنفس لنديا حوالات دولار مجمد من والي جميع دول العالم وجميع شركات الحوالات
سعر الشتر الف دولار اربع الف دولار
يعنى نسبة المبيع 40% اقل منه
يوجد اتفاقية لضمان حق الطرفين واستلام الربون الاموال قبل ما نستلم نحنا...

نمت إرلة الإعلان

حوالات دولار مجمد الي جميع دول العالم
Product Service

إرسال رسالة

حول إخلاء المسؤولية
عندما يصنف أحد المعلنين إعلانه على أنه مرتبط بفضايا اجتماعية أو ترفيهية أو سببية، تتم مطالبة بالإفصاح عن تمويل الإعلان. تعرف على المزيد

معلومات من المعلن

حول الصفحة

عرض الإعلانات

حوالات دولار مجمد الي جميع دول العالم

Deceiving the Promoters

Al-Murjan relies on photographing dollars via mobile phones, sometimes adding paper or a phone to show the date of the day the video was filmed, and sometimes the name of the photographer, and a phone number to communicate with the publisher. The promoter reviews these dollars as being real by highlighting the work of the natural money counting device with those fiat currencies, taking into account that it is possible to disable the feature of detecting counterfeit currencies (p. 8) by turning off this feature on most devices, or by

highlighting the blue tape, the security feature that has been introduced on the [US dollar editions since 2013](#).

By examining these paid videos to promote on Facebook between June 5 and July 5 of 2022, there is a clear similarity between the clips, as shown on the account of pages called "[Al-Marj](#)", "[Al-Mumayaz](#)", "[Sana 'a](#)" and "[Abu Qusay](#)" for the [US dollar](#). On the other hand, the frequent advertisements appear in accounts called "[Sana 'a](#)" and "[Al-Mumayaz](#)" where there are two advertisements, and "[Al-Burag Money Transfer Company](#)" has four advertisements, and the latter takes [an electronic platform](#) under the name of trading and investment.

Abu Qusay USD page

From Al-Nasseri Trading and Investment Company page

From the featured page

of the Sana 'a page

What calls for accuracy in the collection of these videos is the place of filming. Even if the filming time varies, the place of filming is very similar. For example, in the announcement of [Al-Nasseri Trading](#) and [Investment Company](#) on July 2, it shows the same visual features of the video that circulated in the accounts of Sana 'a, Al-Marj, and Al-Mu 'min, and before that, what was published by the page of the [Lebanese Egyptian United Company](#) on June 27, where we find that the places of placing the table, the counting device, and the place of money are similar to all the videos.

This raises two questions: Who is the main photographer of these videos? What is wrong with those accounts that repeatedly promote these videos?

Returning to all videos related to the frozen dollar to search for the oldest video showing the visual features that were observed in more than one account, all reverse image search methods were used, in addition to the repeated circulation of the same clip from several accounts, which makes it difficult to find the first publisher. It is also remarkable that in mid-July many advertising accounts began to trade the same clip from another angle of photography, which is shown, for example, on the Al-Suaibi page. Some advertising accounts

also show the video counting device and the other dimension does not appear, despite the appearance of the rest of the elements similar such as money, hand and needle.

Announcement from Al Masaabi page
'a page

Announcement from Sana

The promotion of the frozen dollar has become a very interesting phenomenon since [2016](#) on Facebook, and this was at the level of pseudonymous personal accounts, and then the matter evolved to create pages with pseudonyms or forged names of official entities in order to use the Facebook advertising feature that was established in [November 2007](#).

This phenomenon is still rife in many social media sites, and even some [free selling platforms](#), and blogs.

But the question remains about Facebook's advertising policy, which is still somewhat in doubt, how it can remove ads without mentioning the reason for some of them while hiding them from the ad library, unlike some other ads in which it mentions the reason for removal.

How does it explain the appearance of some ads on the same page that had an ad previously removed and then reappeared and allowed to be published, as is the case on the page of [Al-Nasseri Trading and Investment Company](#), which republished the same video after the removal of its first ad, as well as how Facebook left some ads without removing them in the first place, as noted on the page of [Al-Buraq Financial Services Company](#), where it funded 16

ads? Several questions can be asked to the management of Facebook, and on the rest of the platforms that are still full of fraud attempts using an attractive phrase such as "frozen dollar".